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Service Process Improvement through VSM of Lean Six Sigma: A Case Study

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Abstract—The paper presents a case study where value stream mapping (VSM) is applied to improve factory-floor employees' performance management process (PMP) in the manufacturing context. The objectives were to 1) understand the PMP of the factory-floor employees, and 2) apply the VSM to improve their PMP. The present study a) identifies value from customers' perspective, b) maps PMP along with its sub-processes, c) analyses waste with the intention of minimization, d) adopts a pull approach to fulfil customers' demands, and e) proposes avenues for perfection. The study showed that notable efficiency improvements can be achieved even by SMEs from the application of VSM and DMAIC (define-measure-analyze-improve-control).

Keywords— service process improvement, value stream mapping, waste reduction

I. INTRODUCTION

Value stream mapping (VSM) offers an in-depth understanding of the 'As-is' state of operations and the improvements needed to create a much desirable 'To-be' state as an essential Lean Six Sigma tool for process improvement. VSM is widely applied to managing manufacturing operations [1, 2]. Although previous studies suggest the potential of applying VSM in service provisions, evidence for its application in service process improvements is limited [3, 4, 5]. Hence, very limited literature is available in this important area in the context of service provision. This paper attempts to fill this void in the literature by presenting a case study where VSM is applied to improve employees' performance management process (PMP) in the manufacturing context.

Performance management as a service provision helps to align employees' outcomes with the organization's goals, placing a greater emphasis on their work execution as well as knowledge, skills and attitudes [6]. If used effectively, performance management is an innovation-creating, problem-solving, and work-motivation method. However, on the one hand, organizations across the continents face challenges with performance management due to not identifying PMP and the existence of waste in PMP [7]. The application of process improvement methodologies and tools could make substantial improvements in service provisions, such as performance management, not only in lean implemented manufacturing [8] and service [7] contexts but also in non-lean implemented service provision contexts [9]. On the other hand, most of the organizations in the world are small to medium in scale in terms of the number of employees engaged.

The present study was conducted in a medium-scale manufacturing plant in Sri Lanka. The objectives of the study were to 1) understand the PMP of the factory-floor employees of the manufacturing plant, and 2) apply VSM to improve their PMP. Accordingly, building on Lean Six Sigma, the present study a) identifies value from customers' perspective, b) maps

PMP along with its sub-processes, c) analyses waste with the intention of minimization, d) adopts a pull approach to fulfil customers' demands, and e) proposes avenues for perfection.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Performance management process

Performance management is at the heart of any organization that strategically manages the performance levels of individuals/teams as well as overall organizational performance [6, 10]. Its main tasks are performance target setting, continuous performance evaluation, and managing performance/underperformance [10]. These activities align with most of the performance management settings [11]. PMP is viewed as an integrated and year-round process where management collaborates with the employees to raise standards, evaluate outcomes, and promote productivity [10]. Hence, with effective use, organizations can recognize, monitor, and improve overall organizational performance by connecting employees' performance to the organization's priorities [6, 12, 13].

B. Value stream mapping

The lean transformations are getting more of a system-based approach, where focus is more on people [1, 4, 7, 14]. When lean tools are applied to people management processes or service provision, theoretical and practical implications of value could be identified [5, 7]. However, since research on the application of lean tools for service provision is limited, well-grounded conceptual models are also limited [3, 15]. Therefore, VSM in service provision is a "starting point for further discussion, research and practical application" [4, p. 961]. When applying VSM in evaluating business processes, identifying SIPOC (supplier, inputs, process, output, and customers) and creating the SIPOC chart are important [5]. In identifying the current state, the use of Gemba walk, 5 whys (asking why repeatedly 5 times whenever a problem is encountered), and 5W2H (Why, what, where, when, who, how, how many/how much) are popular [16]. The evaluation of the current state and meeting the demand in the future state should be based on well-defined matrices such as Takt Time [3, 17]. However, the adoption of this approach is very rare in the service provision [2, 3]. In the present study, VSM is used together with DMAIC (define-measure-analyze-improve-control) as suggested by [2]. The use of VSM together with DMAIC provides a well-grounded approach in the novel context of service provision, especially for employees' performance management in the manufacturing context.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Considering the nature of the investigation, the case study method was used. Table I summarizes the Lean Six Sigma tools used for each stage of DMAIC.

TABLE I. METHOD ADOPTED

Stage	Lean Six Sigma Tools	Purpose
Define	Gemba walk, Document inspection, SIPOC diagram, VSM for the current state	Understand PMP, its components, and boundaries; determine the output and customer requesting the output; map 'As is' or the current state
Measure	Metrics: Takt time, Cycle Time, Queue Time, Lead Time, Processing Time, Error Rate, Value Creation Time	Assess the current state to establish improvements needed for the future state
Analyse	Comparison of Cycle Times against Takt Time Explored waste and root causes with 5 Whys and 5W2H 8 types of waste were identified as per TIMWOODS (Transportation, Inventory, Motion, Waiting, Overproduction, Overprocessing, Defects, and Skills)	Understand the waste of the current state
Improve	VSM for future state, Metrics: Takt time, Cycle Time, Queue Time, Lead Time, Processing Time, Error Rate, Value Creation Time	Map 'To be' or proposed future state; proposals to eliminate waste
Control	Metrics: In addition to the metrics already introduced, Backlog, % timely completed, and Accuracy were also used	Develop a plan to monitor the process to ensure continued success

IV. THE CASE STUDY

The firm where the case study was conducted is a medium-scale apparel manufacturer in Sri Lanka. It undertakes sub-contract orders from large apparel manufacturers serving the export market. Since its workforce is 70 employees in total, it is qualified to be a medium-scale business establishment as per [18]. Under the direct supervision of the manufacturing manager, two supervisors and 50 sewing machine operators were engaged in sewing operations. The PMP of operators can be identified as a generic process consisting of five key tasks, i.e., 1) performance target setting, 2) target acknowledgement, 3) continuous performance evaluation and feedback provision, 4) managing performance/underperformance, and 5) inputs for pay administration. The manufacturing division is responsible for the PMP of operators. Concerning the inputs for pay administration, operators are given incentives for achieving hourly targets. The manufacturing division supplies

the target achievement data of each operator to the administrative officer for the preparation of the monthly payroll. Process maps were created for the main PMP and the subprocesses of the main PMP. All maps are given in Appendix I

V. AS-IS" AND TO-BE" STATES

A. Define

The SIPOC chart created is shown in Table II. VSM for the current state was created. The value-adding analysis is shown in Table III.

B. Measure

Based on the current flow of activities and time taken for each activity, the current state VSM is evaluated as shown in Table IV.

TABLE II. SIPOC CHART

Supplier	Input	Process	Output	Customer
Supervisors	Performance targets	Continuous evaluation of each operator by comparing targets with actuals - hourly and daily	Performance review results of each operator – hourly and daily over a week	Manufacturing manager
Manufacturing manager	Performance review results of each operator – hourly and daily over a week	Preparation of target achievements by each operator hourly and daily over a month	Entitlements for incentive payments for a month	Administrative officer

TABLE III. VALUE-ADDING ANALYSIS

Activity	Value Adding	Non-value Adding
Performance target setting	3 Hours	8 Hours
Targets acknowledgement	2.5 Hours	1.5 Hours
Continuous performance evaluation and feedback provision	1.5 Hours	3.5 Hours
Managing performance/underperformance	2 Hours	1 Hours
Inputs for pay administration	2 Hours	2 Hours
Total	11 Hours	16 Hours

TABLE IV. METRICS OF THE CURRENT STATE VSM

Variable	Unit	Current
Total lead time of the process	Days/Hours	25 Days + 27 Hours = 627 Hours
Total processing time	Days/Hours	27 Hours
Total value-added time of the process	Days/Hours	11 Hours
Overall task efficiency	%	40%
Total time of WIP	Days/Hours	25 Days = 600 Hours
Value Added % Vs total lead time	Percentage	1.8%
Takt time up to monitoring performance/feedback	Hours	12 Hours
Takt time of the complete performance management process	Days	30 Days

C. Analyze

In a typical VSM analysis, the takt time is compared against the cycle times of each stage, and bottlenecks are treated. However, the demand in this process is defined at two stages: the activities up to monitoring of performance and provision of feedback that must be completed daily (12 hours), and the monthly performance management process that must be completed in 30-day cycles. Therefore, in this study, instead of comparing the cycle times of each stage with the takt time, we compare the process lead time up to two stages against their takt time. There was no critical issue as the cycle time of the first three stages is below their takt time of 12 hours. The current total lead time of the process (627 hours) does not create a critical issue, as the takt of the total process is 30 days.

The reduction of inefficient non-value-adding activities is one of the most important expectations of the study. These

non-value-adding activities cause unnecessary stress and traceability issues, despite not having a critical impact on the takt time of the total process. Waste is critically analyzed while carrying out the earlier stages of DMAIC, specifically, define and measure. The mapping of the current state VSM, the value-adding analysis of the current state, and the metrics of the current value stream were used to identify waste. The eight types of waste were identified as per TIMWOODS, which are summarized in Table V.

D. Improve

Analysis led to the identification of potential improvements for the current state of activities. The proposed improvements are shown in Table VI. Based on the proposed future flow of activities and time taken for each activity, the future state VSM is created. Metrics were calculated for the future state. The comparison of the current state and future state metrics is shown in Table VII.

TABLE V. IDENTIFICATION OF WASTE – TIMWOODS

No.	Waste	T	I	M	W	O	O	D	S
Performance target setting									
1	Forms waiting for approval		X						
2	Staff waiting to obtain approvals (due to difficulty in scheduling in-person meetings)				X				
3	Reset/revise targets for each order							X	
4	Lack of criteria to assess operator performance other than the quantity produced							X	X
5	No recognition for exceeding targets							X	X
6	The paper-written reports need to be carried to various departments	X							
7	Discontinuous flow of writing due to poor record formats			X					
8	Unnecessary information in the form (e.g., appear both name and EPF No.)						X		
Acknowledging targets									
9	Supervisors are waiting to get the approvals for the revised targets				X				
10	The records are waiting to get the acknowledgement		X						
Continuous performance evaluation									
11	No method to collect performance records from the operators directly, instead of self-record					X		X	
12	No mechanism to recognize/record the number of reworks during an hour							X	
13	Operators forget to record output every hour							X	
14	Human errors in self-recorded actual output							X	
15	Supervisors must re-record actual hourly output manually on a sheet of paper						X		
16	Human error in the supervisors' record of the hourly output of operators							X	
17	The build-up of unnecessary/duplicate copies at operators and supervisors	X							
18	Manual form filling by supervisors	X					X		
19	Supervisors are devoting time to solving various disruptions, making it difficult to actively supervise								X
20	Misjudgments in measuring hourly output when accounting for other disruptions							X	
21	Supervisors fail to provide the operators' output data to the manufacturing manager every week				X				
22	Improper flow of hourly target achievement data form			X					
23	Re-entering data due to inconsistencies in the data required by the administrative officer						X		
24	Delays in submitting target achievement data to the administrative officer at the end of the month					X			
25	Weekly evaluation of the daily collected data by the supervisors	X							
Feedback provision									
26	A lot of unnecessary materials are discussed, especially with underperformers						X		
27	Feedback provision takes a long time, as there are many operators to give feedback	X							X
28	Excessive searching of data is needed due to the absence of a standard data format			X					
29	Misjudgments on disruptions beyond operators' control (such as machine breakdowns)							X	
Managing performance/underperformance:									
30	Underperformers fail to obtain the required training due to target commitments								X
31	Delay in providing training for underperformers				X				X
32	Lack of follow-up with underperformers due to other errands, such as injuries				X				X
33	Lack of procedures/tools to evaluate underperformance beyond hourly output							X	X
34	Underperformers use a lot of unnecessary motions in performing the job			X					X
35	Recommendation by the manufacturing manager to the administrative officer								X
Inputs for pay administration									
36	The administration section must re-enter target achievement records						X	X	
37	The administration section must return the hourly target records due to errors	X						X	
38	The target achievement record goes back and forth between manufacturing and administration	X							
39	Some operators produce well above the required target to qualify for incentives					X			

TABLE VI. PROPOSED IMPROVEMENTS

No.	Improvement
Performance target setting	
1	Hold consistently Managing Daily Improvement (MDI) meetings/online for approvals
2	Targets should be set based on standard methods and time, such as Standard Minute Values (SMV)
3	An inventory of operators' skill levels (ratings) should be maintained, and work should be allocated accordingly
4	The number of units completed alone is insufficient to evaluate performance; methods such as the SMV earned by each operator can be considered
5	Recognition for surpassing targets and the introduction of efficiency based on the SMV
6	Assign an assistant production manager with good industrial engineering knowledge, mainly for target setting and line balancing
Acknowledging targets	
7	Consistent MDI mechanism for acknowledgement
8	Targets and target achievement status for each order should be communicated on the factory-floor for all operators to be aware of
9	Use good visual aids to communicate information, such as targets and achievements, by fixing display boards
Continuous performance evaluation	
10	Introduce a template for operators/printed form, which can be endorsed by supervisors. As a result, supervisors do not need to re-record actual hourly output
11	Introduce a mechanism to self-record the number of reworks during an hour
12	Revisit incentives to identify underperformers
13	Introduce a mechanism for operators to self-record output every hour to reduce data errors/lack of proper documentation
14	Introduce a simple computer program for supervisors to compare the targets with the actual
15	Introduce error-proofing techniques to improve the quality of products/reduce rework
16	Introduce a safety improvement mechanism using the hierarchy of controls approach to reduce the number of injuries to operators (needle pricks on fingers)
Feedback provision	
17	Provide a pre-structured list to initiate discussion with operators.
18	Provide clear instructions for supervisors to manage discussion time during feedback provision to each operator
Managing performance/underperformance:	
19	Introduce some form of recognition, financial/non-financial, based on the efficiency calculation using SMV. An individual and team incentive system should be carefully selected, as only the individual-based system does not help to achieve targets
20	Reduce the delay between the identification of underperformance and the provision of training
21	Introduce training policy and procedures for operators, and use methods such as standard work presented by video recording
Inputs for pay administration	
22	Introduce an electronic filing system to be shared between the manufacturing division and the administration division for operators' incentive preparation
23	Consider restructuring the operator payment system by introducing an attendance bonus to reduce worker absences/day-offs, irrespective of the order concerned

TABLE VII. METRICS COMPARISON OF THE CURRENT STATE AND FUTURE STATE VSM

Variable	Unit	Current	Future
Total lead time of the process	Days/Hours	25 Days + 27 Hours = 627 Hours	25 Days + 11 Hours = 611 Hours
Total processing time	Days/Hours	27 Hours	11 Hours
Total value-added time of the process	Days/Hours	11 Hours	11 Hours
Overall task efficiency	%	40%	100%
Total time of WIP	Days/Hours	25 Days = 600 Hours	25 Days = 600 Hours
Value Added % Vs total lead time	Percentage	1.75%	1.80%
Takt time up to monitoring performance/feedback	Hours	12 Hours	12 Hours
Takt time of the complete PMP	Days	30 days	30 days

E. Control

The activities of the PMP were visualized using process maps. Process maps further led to visualizing the relationships between PMP and three control policies of the organization, namely, incentive payments, planning for training, and production planning. These policy areas recur in the management literature as important for all organizations irrespective of their size [19, 20, 21].

VSM is a tool for the achievement of a truly lean enterprise. In the application of the VSM and DMAIC method, the present study took processing time as the key performance indicator (KPI) of the PMP of factory-floor employees. Therefore, processing time is the main threshold in the control plan.

VSM demands the organization's commitment to lean, improve its devotion and ability to learn lean concepts and tools, and continuously improve the value stream of PMP.

The continuous identification of waste and setting targets for continuous improvement are the two vital ingredients for gradual improvement and ultimate success. Therefore, it is crucial to closely monitor the improved process and make continuous improvements. In lean management, there is no end to addressing waste, but it is a continuous journey towards perfection. It is important to see the impact of continuous improvement. Therefore, we recommend a new KPI for process efficiency, i.e., VA time/Processing time.

VI. IMPLICATIONS AND PRACTICAL GUIDELINES

The present study was conducted in a manufacturing firm belonging to the category of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). The study showed the importance of applying the Lean Six Sigma tool of VSM for PMP of factory-floor employees. The DMAIC method is used to evaluate the PMP step by step. After understanding the current state, countermeasures were proposed to make improvements in the process. The present study took processing time as the main

KPI of PMP. The study identified potential areas for improvement, which could improve processing times, leading to potential savings in the future state.

The findings of the study are important in several ways. First, the present study addressed an area which has not yet received much attention, i.e., applying Lean Six Sigma tools for the service provision. This research gap is well-presented in [4, 5, 7]. The methodology adopted (given in Table I) led to the better identification of the current process, wastes involved, and avenues for perfection. The study is different from [3, 4, 5] since we showed the application of Lean Six Sigma tools and the DMAIC method for the service provision. We selected one of the human resource management processes, i.e., performance management, as the service process. Further, we applied Lean Six Sigma tools and the DMAIC method to an organization that can be identified as an SME.

Second, we showed that the improvements in processing times are visible with the methodology adopted. Therefore, the findings underline the importance of identifying avenues for perfecting PMP to maximize human potential in the factory-floor. The application of VSM in this service provision showed the applicability of Lean Six Sigma tools beyond the manufacturing process. The concept and tools of Lean Six Sigma showed avenues for it to evolve when applied in service provisions. When considering human-centric business operations, either in the manufacturing or service context, employees' performance is an important consideration in process improvement efforts. Therefore, the application of VSM and DMAIC in the service process improvement is the most novel contribution of the present study.

Third, reducing the time consumed in human-centric manufacturing processes is a major concern in the production context. Although important, reducing the time consumed by non-production and administrative activities receive limited attention in most manufacturing contexts. The present study showed the potential avenues to substantially reduce the time consumed by non-production, administrative activities concerning factory-floor employees. We showed that 1) the optimization of the utilization of supervisory and administrative personnel positively contributes to operational efficiency, and 2) the time savings achieved in pre-production administrative processes have an even more significant downstream impact on production operations. For instance, expediting administrative tasks enables production teams to commence work earlier, thereby facilitating the achievement of committed production lead times and alleviating time pressure on production staff. Consequently, improvements in pre-production administrative activities enhance the organization's ability to meet customer deadlines more reliably.

Fourth, in this research, we demonstrated the potential to reduce the processing time of a performance management process from 27 hours to 11 hours, indicating a theoretical task efficiency improvement of over 100%. While such a figure may appear overly ambitious, our findings suggest that significant efficiency gains can be realized through the careful identification and elimination of non-value-adding activities, often via straightforward and low-cost interventions. These findings are particularly relevant for SMEs aiming for rapid growth, where complex and lengthy bureaucratic processes can act as a significant barrier.

Fifth, the present study was conducted in the apparel industry. It is noteworthy that, within the apparel industry, only approximately 20% of the total lead time is typically spent on actual sewing operations. This underscores the necessity of addressing the disproportionately long durations associated with non-production tasks. Our study highlights this critical implication and emphasizes the importance of future research focusing on the streamlining of administrative processes, particularly in industries where market competitiveness is increasingly determined by the ability to meet shorter lead times.

Sixth, from a broader perspective, the issue of non-productive administrative tasks is not confined to apparel manufacturing alone. We propose that similar methodologies, particularly the application of VSM, can be effectively employed across various industrial and service sectors to identify and minimize inefficiencies in administrative workflows. This approach may hold particular value for public sector organizations, where most operations are administrative in nature and process efficiency is often the most crucial in service delivery.

Seventh, the findings illustrate the benefits of the proposed methodology, i.e., the application of VSM and DMAIC, for SMEs. Most of the workplaces in the world come under the category of SME. The present study shows that notable efficiency improvements can be achieved even by SMEs through the application of VSM and DMAIC. When VSM is applied to PMP in SMEs, it underlines the importance of maximizing human potential, identifying avenues for perfecting the service value stream, applying pull and flow to service provisions, and turning the focus of lean tools beyond the manufacturing process to identify avenues for lean to further evolve. Further, process maps helped to visualize the relationships between PMP and the firm's control policies of incentive payments, planning for training, and production planning. These three policy areas are found to be vital for SMEs [22, 23, 24], and improvements covering these policy areas could lead to ultimate organizational success. Still, as suggested in [25, 26], individuals leading the organizations may need development opportunities for better implementation of process improvement methodologies and tools. Further, as suggested in [27], their leadership capabilities must be developed to enhance innovative applications in dynamic business environments.

Finally, countries like Sri Lanka and Bangladesh highly rely on export apparel manufacturing, and the implementation of process improvement methodologies helps tremendously to reduce costs in the final export product [28]. We applied the value stream mapping to the PMP of factory-floor machine operators of an apparel manufacturer. The job of factory-floor machine operator and the job holders' performance are imperative for the achievement of production targets, revenue earned, and future business success. Although managing human resources is of utmost importance in business operations, the adoption of lean tools for human resource processes is very rare. The PMP is managed as a cost centre worldwide. Organizations focus on streamlining the operations of profit centres (like production divisions) to reduce costs further. Hence, huge potential exists to streamline the operations of cost centres (like human resources). We believe the findings of the present study may attract considerable attention to streamlining the operations of human resource management processes (like performance

management) with the intention of cost savings. Any type of savings, like processing times, can make product/service offerings of any business more competitive in the consumer markets.

VII. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

First, the future state is proposed considering the avenues for perfection. The suggested improvements may yield expected time savings when PMP is implemented correctly. With more data inputs, such as hourly payments for employees, direct savings with reductions in task completion times on employee remuneration could be derived. Second, since the paper presents a case study, the findings lack generalization. However, the methodology proposed in the paper can be applied in almost all employee PMP contexts. Third, proposed improvements can have practical implications and challenges since these involve changes to the current system. Managing resistance to change and providing training to smoothly transfer into the proposed system are important. These are not investigated in the present study and are open for future research.

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Appendix 1

SERVICE PROCESS IMPROVEMENT THROUGH VSM OF LEAN SIX SIGMA: A CASE STUDY

Fig. 1. Main PMP process

Fig.1a. Process map for performance target setting and target acknowledgement

Fig. 1b. Process map for continuous performance evaluation and feedback provision

Fig. 1c. Process map for managing performance/underperformance and inputs for pay administration

Fig. 2. Current state VSM

Fig. 3. Future state VSM